

CHANGE AND CHANGE MANAGEMENT - UNLOCKING POWER FLEXIBILITY MEETING SWEDEN'S CAPACITY CHALLENGE

John BACKE

E.ON Energidistribution AB – Sweden
John.backe@eon.se

David BJARUP

E.ON Energidistribution AB – Sweden
David.bjarup@eon.se

Yvonne RUWAIDA

Vattenfall Eldistribution AB - Sweden
Yvonne.ruwaida@vattenfall.com

ABSTRACT

The electricity market in Sweden is changing to accommodate new trends in energy production and electrification. A potential hurdle presents itself in the change management. We have much to gain by realizing the massive challenges this brings, and in understanding the behavioural change on individuals and in organisations that lies ahead. Through leveraging previous learning on unlocking flexibility, bilateral treaties and digital markets, the DSOs can achieve the energy transition and realize a more efficient and sustainable capacity utilization in the power grids.

INTRODUCTION

The Swedish energy system is in some respects a role model for market design, power system stability, and high penetration of renewables. This system is currently experiencing two simultaneous trends: a shift towards even higher levels of renewables, and a continuous wave of electrification in manufacturing, transportation and new types of energy intensive industries.

THE SWEDISH GRID AND THE ELECTRICITY MARKET

In Sweden, most electricity is produced by hydroelectric power plants (41%) and nuclear power plants (40%). Since the largest rivers are in the northernmost parts of Sweden, most hydropower is generated where population density and demand is the lowest. The electrical grid structure therefore needs to handle redistribution from north to south, and over long distances. Dense urban regions are also more dependent on CHP generation, which accounts for 10% of net electricity production in Sweden (2016). [1] Sweden is also a net exporter of electricity.

Wind turbines generate 10% of Swedish power, a number that is expected to rise in the coming years due to increased investments in renewable energy and DER in general. Intermittent generation, such as wind turbines and solar PV, presents new challenges and stresses the grid on both TSO and DSO levels. Export of electricity creates new flow patterns in the transmission grid that changes the capacity situation locally. [2]

While installed capacity for DER is increasing rapidly, nuclear reactors and cogeneration CHPs are closing. The trend is that CHPs are closing to phase out fossil fuel, and then replaced with regular heating plants without power production due to low electricity prices reducing the cost-efficiency of cogeneration. [3]

Overall, energy consumption in Sweden is close to fossil free and provides consumers and industry with clean power at relatively low cost. [4]

In Sweden the DSO is organized into two levels: the local network (up to 50 kV) also called the DSO distribution network, and the regional network (normally between 70 kV-130 kV) called the DSO transmission network. To avoid outages, a region can import more power from another, such as the northern parts of Sweden where generation potential is higher. Sweden is divided into four bidding areas to facilitate these kinds of transactions.

The Swedish TSO Svenska Kraftnät (Svk) is responsible for maintaining balance between power input and output, so that the frequency is kept at 50 Hz with minimal deviation. To achieve this, Svk functions as a broker between BRPs using ancillary services regulated in a Systems Operations Agreement (SOA).

Figure 1 - Bidding zones

NEW POWER DEMANDS

In Sweden we have a trend of higher demand stemming from digitalization, electrification in the form of data centers, battery production and EV charging. Both new actors and existing customers are requesting more capacity, while also striving to become fossil free. At the same time an unprecedented and rapid increase in housing development is taking place. The Swedish government have signed agreements for future expansion or establishment of nine urban areas. These agreements are combined with large investments in railway and trams, as well as ambitions for fossil free transportation and heating. [5]

To smaller electricity consumers the process of getting connected to the grid is much faster than for power customers with higher demands. Connection of bigger loads often entail more complex grid analysis and the need for subscription raises, that in turn involves the transmission grid on both the regional and national level. During the last 20 years - except for the latest two years - DSOs have had fewer large customers to plan for, and those actors have been well aware of the lead time needed for planning.

The requests of these new types of customers have proven much more urgent than traditional grid planning processes allows for, and their demands on capacity and availability are less predictable as well. Traditionally, the infrastructure of power distribution in Sweden involves long-term planning in 50-year cycles, which is not compatible with current trends. Lead times to build new transmission grid infrastructure have risen to 5-7 years at the regional level, and 10-15 years for the transmission grid.

The TSO/DSOs are focusing on achieving full capacity to last in extreme scenarios, e.g. a 10-year long winter. They are also accustomed to having complete command of power distribution in their allotted “zones of control”. All in all, recent developments are challenging the traditional notion of grid capacity as something exclusively dedicated and immutable, and instead giving rise to increased interaction.

The world is experiencing an increase in extreme weather, which also affects the production and power flow in the grid. The summer of 2018 was uniquely hot and dry in Sweden, reducing output of hydropower plants and further exacerbating energy shortages, as well as resulting in a surge in electrical prices for the underpowered regions. [6]

Available capacity in the transmission grid is affected by exporting electricity, creating new and problematic flow patterns. These factors all contribute to growing issues with bottlenecks and congestion in the grid. More

specifically we are seeing capacity shortages locally in the transmission grid, mostly at TSO level but occasionally at DSO level, affecting the subscription allowed between TSO and DSO grids and between the regional DSO and local DSO grids. At present the issue is an issue of capacity shortage in the grid, it is not related to the national power balance regulated by Svk, but this is expected to change after 2030.

THE CAPACITY CHALLENGE

At the TSO level, the 220 kV grid linking hydropower in the north of Sweden with the more urban southern half is showing its age. More intermittent production, new flows in the transmission grid and new demands on capacity necessitates significant changes. [7] Improvements in grid structure are planned but will arrive too late, on account of the accelerating power demands created by the paradigm shift towards renewable, fossil free energy and towards digitalized society. If industry demands on power capacity cannot be met in a timely manner, companies will expand elsewhere or leave Sweden entirely. The calculated cost of the capacity limitations in the grid (not in production per se) for Sweden is estimated to around 8B€ per year and could reach 15B€ in 2030 unless the situation improves. To put the numbers in context, 15B€ is close to the net worth of the entire grid structure in Sweden. [8]

It is a fact that the Swedish grid is facing existing and growing large scale network constraints in the DSO/TSO interface and in the regional DSO grid. This is a critical challenge that the power grid companies are trying to solve through conventional investments in capacity reinforcements. However urgent and necessary, this approach is not sufficient on its own. That is why DSOs are investigating and developing capabilities to deploy flexibility, i.e. using shifts in the loads of energy producers and consumers to alleviate congestions. Unlocking and implementing flexibility in an efficient way is expected to optimize utilization of the grid, whilst meeting the expectations of the utility and consumer stakeholders.

FLEXIBILITY IN THE PAST AND ON THE ELECTRICITY MARKET

The idea of flexible power customers is not a new one. Prior to the deregulation of the energy sector in Sweden in the mid-1990s, there were hundreds of remotely controlled power boilers across Sweden, with specific tariffs for interruptible loads. Today there are also customers already active as flexibility sources both individually or via VPPs, providing flexibility day-ahead or intraday. This is taking place on the electricity market meeting the TSO need of frequency balancing.

LEARNINGS FROM PREVIOUS PROJECTS IN NEAR TIME

The two Swedish DSOs Vattenfall and E.ON have made different but related learnings on using flexibility for DSO purposes, solving more local needs than addressed by the four Swedish bidding zones. The electricity price does not function as a price signal solving the local capacity shortage.

The learnings are made in two separate projects, coming from two different perspectives in the flexibility domain. The projects have focused on using network-based flexibility services in the DSO regional network and DSO local network for a more efficient use of the power grid to release available capacity. *Vattenfall Eldistribution AB* has tested congestion management by unlocking power flexibility through bilateral treaties for load and production steering, and *E.ON Energidistribution AB* has developed and tested digital market places. Results from these endeavors are analyzed to identify some of the barriers that will be faced in the effort of unlocking power flexibility.

In both organizations and contexts similar and complementary insights have been made. The insights support the validity of a wide and thorough approach for a sustainable implementation of flexibility. In the DSO context, flexibility as a solution to congestion management was shown to be a feasible option. However, many challenges arise in the process of seamlessly integrating flexibility as a functioning option in the operation context, where operators are unfamiliar with making day-ahead decisions and lack data, routines and systems for such new paradigms. The nature of flexibility as a service, as opposed to a physical and tangible asset is not to be underestimated as it presents a new type of risk. As a consequence, the introduction of multiple flexible customers is not feasible with today's support system on larger scale.

Grid planning presents a similar case. How can and should flexibility, with all its uncertainties, be valued against physical capacity on a 12 month or ten-year horizon? To cope with this, new risk assessment models and tools have been developed. Unlocking flexibility in the electricity grid also increases risk. Instead of the usual approach of factoring in failure cases at nominal operation, flexibility acts as an emergency valve in case of failure; presently this is handled manually. This functionality is a novel concept that brings higher risk in the context of grid planning and operation.

In dealing with bilateral contracts between consumers and producers of flexibility, compliance management and careful planning is necessary to ensure integration with future grid development. Without this support structure, bilateral treaties would result in very time-consuming and

manual work. Overall, the nature of these contracts makes them more suitable for specific, smaller-scale agreements.

Due to the slow-moving nature of structural development, research and cooperation are essential tools in developing more dynamic strategies that is viable in the near future, while also providing TSO/DSOs with a solid base for long-term planning.

In the client context, we have seen that customers as well as society are unaccustomed to analyzing, understanding and planning for power flexibility. For them climate emissions, energy efficiency and electricity and fuel price are factors they are used to analyzing, understanding and planning around. The need for stimulants and incentives beyond a business case is vital to unlock flexibility for congestion management, since market-based ancillary services would seldom be a core business for all possible flexibility players. The TSO and DSO must give the customers comprehensible information about the business case of unlocking flexibility and the future increased pricing of power. In addition, society should give a clear signal that unlocking power flexibility is desirable and important. All this is new for all actors and needs.

A totally new issue in the Swedish DSO context is how to value flexibility from small aggregated loads. It is very complex but also very important if we are to unlock all possible flexibility. Also, the follow-up of customers in general is a new issue that needs new processes and system support to manage on larger scale.

Coordination is needed between DSO – TSO – customer as well as with balance responsible parties for an efficient use of power flexibility. This coordination is not currently in place, neither is an understanding of congestion issues in relation to the electricity market.

TOWARDS MARKET PLACES FOR SYSTEM AND FLEXIBILITY SERVICES

To be able to unlock flexibility, it is not enough to implement market-based ancillary services – change and change management in the areas of operating, planning, forecasting as a tool, TSO-DSO coordination, flexibility product development and customer engagement are also needed. We also believe a firm understanding of local circumstances is critical to implementing flexibility at all necessary levels.

Together with our partners (see further acknowledgments below) Vattenfall Eldistribution, E.ON Energidistribution and Svenska Kraftnät are creating market places as large scale demonstrations in the CoordiNET project, which is focused on joining all the different pieces and creating a holistic approach to unlock flexibility.

Figure 2 - A wide approach on transformation, multiple technologies and perspectives are needed to drive change in order to achieve a local flexibility market

In the scope of the market places, Vattenfall, E.ON and Svk will look at all the issues within the Swedish energy market, not just from a technical or engineering perspective but will take into account cultural, political and financial aspects as well. Insights from the research-heavy first stages of CoordiNET will be utilized in live demonstrations in Sweden, enabling DSO and customer flexibility through a digital marketplace.

CoordiNET will effectively establish new pathways between flexibility providers such as DERs (both aggregated into VPPs and autonomously) and flexibility users, i.e. TSO and DSO.

Comillas, Iberdrola, Red Electrica de Espana, Fundacion Tecnia, Nuestra Nueva Energia, Ayuntamiento de Málaga, Vattenfall Eldistribution, E.ON Energidistribution, Svenska Kraftnät, Uppsala Kommun, Energiforsk, Expektra, Rheinisch-Westfaelische Technische Hochschule Aachen, Diacheiristis Ellinikou Diktyou Dianomis Elektrikis Energeias, Independent Power Transmission Operator, Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek, N-side, Engineering – Ingegneria Informatica, Offis, European Distribution Systems Operators for Smart Grids, Etra Investigacion y Desarrollo.

MISCELLANEOUS

Glossary

DSO: Distribution System Operator
 DER: Distributed Energy Resources
 TSO: Transmission System Operator
 CHP: Combined Heat and Power
 BRP: Balance Responsible Party
 SOA: Systems Operations Agreement
 EV: Electric Vehicle
 VPP: Virtual Power Plant
 AI: Artificial Intelligence
 Flexibility services: Term used in the directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on common rules for the internal market in electricity for flexibility used by the DSO

Acknowledgments

CoordiNET project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement n° 824414. The Consortium Members are hereby acknowledged for their contribution and participation in the project: Endesa,

REFERENCES

- [1] Karin Byman, 2015, "Elproduktion – Tekniker för produktion av el", IVA, Stockholm, Sweden, 7. <https://www.iva.se/globalassets/info-trycksaker/vagval-el/vagval-el-elproduktion.pdf>
 - [2] Energimyndigheten, 2018, "Energy in Sweden, facts and figures 2018", Eskilstuna, Sweden. http://www.energimyndigheten.se/globalassets/statistik/energilaget/energy-in-sweden-2018_20180419.xlsx
 - [3] John Hallbeck et al., 2018, "Pre Study – The Malmö Effect", Energimyndigheten, Malmö, Sweden, 12.
- Energimyndigheten, 2016, "Långsiktiga scenarier", Eskilstuna, Sweden. <http://www.energimyndigheten.se/statistik/prognoser-och-scenarier/?currentTab=1#mainheading>
- Uniper press release, 2018, "Uniper ansöker om tillstånd för permanent stängning av Öresundsverket

i Malmö”.

<http://www.mynewsdesk.com/se/uniper/pressreleases/uniper-ansoeker-om-tillstaand-foer-permanent-staengning-av-oeresundsverket-i-malmoe-2534593>

- [4] Elproduktion med fossila bränslen i EU
<https://www.ekonomifakta.se/Fakta/Energi/Energibalans-internationellt/Elproduktion-med-fossila-branslen/?graph=/7197/1/all/>

Statistik över elpriser

https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Electricity_price_statistics/sv#Elpriser_f.C3.B6r_icke-hush.C3.A5llskonsumenter

- [5] Pöyry, 2017, ”Trångt i elnäten – Ett hinder för omställning och tillväxt?”, Stockholm, Sweden, 8-9.
<https://www.energiforetagen.se/globalassets/energiforetagen---spara-inte-bilder-har/nyheter/2018/2018-08-16-poyryrapporten.pdf?v=lquN8eBVVgH9r3eJQjyA64fTUw0>

Regeringskansliet, 2017, ”Slutredovisning av Uppdrag att samordna större samlade exploateringar med hållbart byggande”, Stockholm, Sweden.

<https://www.regeringen.se/4912ec/contentassets/d4b521ba86ea4ed491195dd6e1b6bdc7/slutredovisning-utredningen-for-storre-samlade-exploateringar.pdf>

- [6] Kjell Gustafsson, 2018-10-26, ”Torkan minskade vattenkraften”, SVT, Sweden.
<https://www.svt.se/nyheter/lokalt/varmland/torkan-minskade-vattenkraften>
- [7] Svenska Kraftnät, 2017, ”Systemutvecklingsplan 2018-2027”, Stockholm, Sweden, 58.
<https://www.svk.se/siteassets/om-oss/rapporter/2017/svenska-kraftnats-systemutvecklingsplan-2018-2027.pdf>

- [8] Pöyry, 2017, ”Trångt i elnäten – Ett hinder för omställning och tillväxt?”, Stockholm, Sweden, 24.